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ISQCMC '25

3rd International Symposium on Quantum Computing and Musical Creativity (ISQCMC '25)

Music Abstract Booklet

Edited by

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This booklet contains the abstracts extracted from the accepted manuscripts submitted for the *Music* track of ISQCMC '25. The manuscripts for the ISQCMC '25 Music track were reviewed by the conference Organizational Team. The accepted works were programmed and performed at the event venue, Sala Lanza, Orto Botanico, University of Palermo, Italy on October 28 of 2025. Each entry lists the title, authors, affiliations, and the abstract.

Quantum Guitar

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Abstract. The concept of **Quantum Guitar** is as follows: A guitar string represents a wave, and by associating a qubit to each of its playable states we get a quantum wave. In order to achieve this quantisation of a guitar, we couple a guitar with Moth's Actias quantum synth, and for qubit manipulations including measurements one uses foot controllers, hence using all four limbs like a drummer. **Quantum Guitar** also allows for smooth continuous transition from 'quantum' to 'classical' sound. Hence a **Quantum Guitar** truly is a canonical 'quantization' of a guitar, with the extra quantum degrees of freedom accounted for by pedals, that require development of new skills besides ordinary guitar playing. Hence **Quantum Guitar** is truly a new musical instrument.

Q-Bars

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* Supported by Moth.

Abstract. Using the various Simulated Quantum Gate Distortions (SQGDs) written about in "Simulating Quantum Gate Distortion Effects with the Quantum Audio Python Package", I composed a 2.5 minute piece entitled **Q-Bars** that incorporates 4 various distortion effects. Alongside the **Q-Bars** audio, there are 5 smaller musical demos to hear the post processed audio of a 14 second jazz keyboard lick (i) classically without distortion, (ii) with the bell state, (iii) flipped bell state, (iv) CNOT, and (v) GHZ state distortions. The pipeline for generating these post processed audio signals involves first the QPAM (Quantum Probability Amplitude Modulation) encoding, then the distortion created through unitary gates, followed by statevector extraction as a substitute to measuring and decoding the circuit. **Q-Bars** as a piece features a rap verse describing the pipeline for the SQGD where each of the 14 musical tracks features one of the 4 various distortions within the SQGD.

Quantum Loops

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Abstract. Inspired by the equivalence of loops on tori, as topologically-protected logical operators in the Kitaev surface codes, I developed an Eulerian tonnetz-based iterative composition method for evolving melodic motifs into progressively simpler residues. The resulting compositions aurally realize the critical concept of topological equivalence of loops on tori and will be performed live during the event in an acoustic solo flute performance.

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Abstract. In recent years, emerging research at the intersection of quantum physics and sound has opened new conceptual and technical possibilities for instrument design and sonic exploration. This study investigates the potential of formal analogies between quantum systems and classically non-deterministic systems for the generation of tangible acoustic phenomena. Specifically, it explores how quantum mechanical concepts can serve not only as metaphors but as operative frameworks in the design of new musical tools. The project is structured in two interconnected phases: (1) the design of a physical instrument based on the stochastic excitation of a vibrating string, capturing analogies with coherent quantum states; and (2) the development of a real-time digital signal processing (DSP) model that uses precomputed quantum simulations to modulate the spectral content of the instrument’s output. These simulations are derived from the quantum harmonic oscillator (QHO), a model that also serves as a foundation for continuous-variable quantum computing and, when modified by nonlinear couplings, can act as a qubit platform in quantum information systems. The resulting system enables live, dynamic interaction with simulated quantum dynamics, offering new forms of timbral control and expressivity. Preliminary tests demonstrate that quantum spectral modulations generate perceptually rich and differentiated textures, especially when using coherent superposition (kitten) states. This work contributes to a field of quantum music creation by offering a hybrid artistic–scientific platform with potential applications in live performance, experimental composition, and science education.

Showcase of the $\langle escrita|excrita \rangle$ performance

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Abstract. This work showcases the recording of the Quantum Computer Music concert that occurred in 4 of September 2025 on the occasion of the Ars Electronica Festival 2025. The performance marks a milestone in the field of Quantum Computer Music, combining several of techniques developed in the past 4 years and implementing hybrid quantum-classical techniques in a complex, poetic and multi-layered way. The video recording of the performance at Ars Electronica, together with a remastered audio recording, will be reproduced and showcased at the ISQCMC conference.

quantum music #001

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Abstract. In this project, sonification and electroacoustic composition techniques to represent simulated controlled quantum dynamics were first explored in a piece composed in 2014. An intuitive sonification process was suggested in order to represent, acoustically and musically, an important quantum phenomenon that is used in quantum computation. An interesting problem in this field has been to understand why states float back and forth between a number of configurations, seemingly unguided, and yet almost miraculously reach the target eventually. Through Parameter-Mapping Sonification, the dynamics of this microscopic and peculiar system were explored. In the current research, the sonification choices have both a functional and an aesthetic goal.

(position xor velocity) redux

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Abstract. This document describes the preparation, software, peripheral layout for performance, synthetic score, and instructions for the execution of a short suite in four movements titled **(position xor velocity) is unknown**. The suite is compositionally based on Heisenberg's uncertainty principle and belongs to the field of Quantum Computer Music through its use of quantum algorithms to generate some of the parameters characterizing a single performance (event) of the composition .

The Veil

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Abstract. **The Veil** is a live algorithmic composition utilizing the sonification of a quantum binary optimiser algorithm (QUBO), using the Variational Quantum Harmonizer (VQH), developed by the QuTune Project and German Electron Synchrotron (DESY). In the composition, VQH is used both as a mean of sound generation using wavetable additive synthesis and as a stochastic sequencer for playing out the notes of a scale, that slowly converge to the chord notes. Through these means, it investigates practical ways to integrate quantum computational algorithms in live music, while presenting an alternative sonification method for the QUBO algorithm using wavetable additive synthesis.

The Sound of Entanglement.

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Abstract. The second quantum revolution as an audiovisual spectacle: lasers, mirrors, and nonlinear crystals form an experimental setup from a high-tech laboratory live on stage. A laser generates entangled pairs of light particles, known as photons. Entangled particles lose their individual properties but maintain a particularly strong relationship with each other, no matter how far apart they are. Albert Einstein called this phenomenon “spooky action at a distance.” The Nobel Prize in Physics in 2022 was awarded for experiments that demonstrated this behavior. Today, entanglement is the backbone of modern information technologies such as quantum computing and quantum cryptography.

In **The Sound of Entanglement**, the entangled photon pairs take on the role of a conductor. Measurement data are translated into musical notation and synthetic sounds that the musicians interact with in real time. Together with live visuals controlled by the quantum experiment, this creates a sensual symbiosis of music, visual art, and modern research. The performance is preceded by a short and accessible physics mini-lecture that explains entanglement and shows how the experiment can be used to create art.

Seeking: High Mountains and Flowing Water

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Abstract. This work statement is submitted in conjunction with the conference technical paper, with the two complementing and reinforcing each other. The research team conducted functional optimization of quantum gates and developed an automatic composition controller for the Q1 Quantum Synthesizer developed by the Miranda team in the United Kingdom. Furthermore, the team explored the construction of a closed-loop performance model of “gesture–quantum sound–instrument interaction,” marking an early attempt at quantum computer music in China. **Seeking: High Mountains and Flowing Water** takes the traditional Chinese guzheng piece **High Mountains and Flowing Water** as its source material, integrating classical Chinese sonic-visual imagery with quantum computer music, thereby creating a hybrid electronic work for the Q1 Quantum Synthesizer and guzheng. The performance form of the work has been experimentally verified, and its premiere took place at the International Computer Music Conference (ICMC) 2024, Seoul, representing a pioneering Chinese contribution to the emerging field of quantum computer music.
